

CATALYTIC CLEANING OF EXHAUST GASES FROM VARIOUS INDUSTRIES AND MOTOR TRANSPORT

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Abstract. *This article highlights the problems and solutions of catalytic cleaning of exhaust gases from various industries and motor transport on low-percentage palladium and vanadium-containing catalysts. The most economical method of cleaning exhaust gases from various impurities is proposed.*

Keywords: *air atmosphere, catalytic cleaning, exhaust gases, carbon oxides, nitrogen, sulfur, hydrocarbons.*

Introduction. Environmental protection is one of the most important problems of our time. Nature protection as an important component of the socio-economic development of society in our country is given great attention. The Decisions of the State of the Republic of Uzbekistan note "to strengthen the protection of atmospheric air. For these purposes, improve technological processes, equipment and vehicles, improve the quality of raw materials and fuel, introduce highly efficient installations for cleaning industrial and other emissions." The Law "On the Protection of Atmospheric Air" imposes high requirements on the purification of gas emissions and the creation of effective cleaning methods. The main source of air pollution are thermal power plants, industrial enterprises and motor vehicles, which account for the bulk of sulfur dioxide, organic compounds, carbon monoxide (II) and nitrogen oxides. Currently, a number of methods have been developed for cleaning industrial gas emissions from sulfur dioxide. An unambiguous solution to this problem is impossible, since the composition of the exhaust gases and the content of dioxide, sulfur in them varies widely with different temperatures.

Purification of sulfur dioxide using the liquid phase - "wet processes" is carried out at relatively low temperatures and causes a number of difficulties:

- a decrease in the temperature of the exhaust gases and their saturation with water vapor;
- deterioration in the operating mode of the smoke stacks, due to a decrease in the lifting force of the gases;
- complexity of the technological design of the process; - insufficiently high degree of purification.

For "dry" cleaning (adsorption, adsorption-catalytic and catalytic) there is no temperature limitation, however, adsorption and adsorption-catalytic methods have high operating and energy costs.

Methodology. In domestic and foreign practice of cleaning low-concentration gases of variable composition from sulfur dioxide, preference is given to catalytic oxidation to trioxide with the production of sulfuric acid or other sulfur-containing products. For the oxidation of sulfur

dioxide, industrial vanadium catalysts, catalysts based on iron, chromium, tin, etc. are proposed (Novocherkassk Polytechnic and Engineering and Land Reclamation Institutes, LTI named after Lensovet).

One of the effective methods for freeing exhaust gases from carbon monoxide (II) and hydrocarbons is their deep oxidation to CO₂ and H₂O. The latter is successfully carried out on mixed palladium-containing catalysts (Institute of Organic Chemistry and Quantum Chemistry of the Kazakh Academy of Sciences), copper-chromium (Institute of Soil Chemistry of the Russian Academy of Sciences), palladium-vanadium, titanium-containing (Pisarzhevsky Institute of Physical Chemistry of the Ukrainian Academy of Sciences), spent aluminoplatinum (Dzerzhinsky branch of the Research Institute of Gases and Gases and Chemistry of the Russian Academy of Sciences), manganese-palladium (Institute of Chemical Chemistry of the Russian Academy of Sciences) and other catalysts. The most common method of cleaning industrial and motor vehicle emissions from nitrogen oxides is their catalytic reduction to molecular nitrogen. In the nitrogen industry, selective and high-temperature methods have been developed (GIAP) and mastered on a large scale. Currently, selective ammonia purification on the AVK-10 catalyst operates at old nitric acid plants with low-productivity individual equipment, and a more advanced one is used at nitric acid plants according to the AK-72M scheme on an aluminum-zinc-copper catalyst (ATsMK-10).

High-temperature purification with natural gas on the APK-2 aluminum-palladium catalyst is used in nitric acid plants according to the UKL-69 and AK-72 schemes.

The main reason for the high temperature of the catalytic purification process from nitrogen oxides (even in the case of highly active catalysts) is the use of natural gas as a reducing gas. Therefore, the development of low-temperature purification from nitrogen oxides is relevant.

Hydrogen is a highly active reducing gas, and its use makes it possible to organize a low-temperature process and use catalysts that do not contain precious metals or have a low content of them. However, with hydrogen consumption corresponding to the stoichiometric ratio of hydrogen to oxygen of 2, hydrogen-containing gas cannot be presented at existing enterprises, since this will lead to a reduction in capacity for the main product and is not economically justified.

Reducing hydrogen consumption for purification by using hydrocarbons present in the composition of the exhaust gases and organizing a relatively selective purification process with a ratio of $H_2 / O_2 = \text{less than } 2$ is of practical interest.

The exhaust gases of a number of industries (bitumen from high-sulfur oils, nitrosyl sulfuric and nitric acids, phosphogypsum burning, lamination of furniture boards with urea-formaldehyde resins, agglomeration gases of the metallurgical industry, flue gases of the primary reforming of natural gas, etc.) contain several components at the same time, for example, SO₂ and CO, NO, C_nH_m in various combinations. An effective method of complex purification of multi-component sulfur-containing exhaust gases is their catalytic oxidation to harmless or easily removable substances. However, catalysts for the complete oxidation of carbon monoxide (II) and hydrocarbons are ineffective in oxidizing sulfur dioxide, and catalysts for the oxidation of sulfur dioxide do not provide complete purification from carbon monoxide (II) and hydrocarbons.

In the catalytic purification of multicomponent gases containing nitrogen oxides, hydrocarbons, carbon monoxide (II) and sulfur oxides, some of them CO, C_nH_m can serve as a reducing agent, and sulfur oxides will have a toxic effect on the catalyst.

Results and discussion. The processing of sulfur-containing gases contaminated with

fluorine impurities on industrial vanadium catalysts is not possible due to the deactivation of the catalyst by fluorine. In this regard, the selection and development of the most active, heat-resistant and inexpensive catalysts for the oxidation of sulfur dioxide, resistant to the action of fluorine compounds, makes it possible to expand the raw material base for sulfuric acid. Thus, the processing of sulfur-containing exhaust gases with the simultaneous neutralization of associated harmful components, as well as the purification of industrial gas emissions containing carbon monoxide (II), hydrocarbons, nitrogen oxides and traces of sulfur compounds, are of great importance for the national economy.

Complex purification of multicomponent exhaust gases should be preceded by a study of individual stages of the processes, which include joint transformations to harmless and easily removed substances. The solution to these problems is important from both an economic and social point of view and is an example of solving a major national economic problem. The aim of our research was to develop and create effective and economic methods for cleaning multicomponent industrial waste gases from carbon monoxide (II), hydrocarbons, nitrogen oxides in the presence of sulfur dioxide and from sulfur dioxide in the presence of fluoride compounds, which was achieved by:

- using low-percentage displaced palladium-containing and spent aluminoplatinum catalysts, determining the optimal conditions for their operation;
- developing new catalytic systems based on carriers modified with water-soluble polymers;
- identifying kinetic patterns of oxidation and reduction of multicomponent gas mixtures;
- creating kinetic models and their use for calculating reactors of industrial gas purification plants.

Conclusion. Within the framework of oxidation-reduction processes occurring during catalytic conversion of multicomponent mixtures, the issues of mutual influence of carbon monoxide (II), propane-butane and sulfur dioxide were considered; nitrogen oxide (II), cyclohexane, hydrogen, oxygen and sulfur dioxide, formaldehyde and sulfur dioxide on known and developed catalysts.

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